

Monitoring Ponte Moesa Campagnola

Final Report

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Monitoring Ponte Moesa Campagnola: Final Report

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Abstract

This document reports on the conceptualization, installation procedure and the cumulative results of the monitoring campaign conducted on the Ponte Moesa Campagnola (TI). This study enables the evaluation of monitoring technologies and associated data-driven analysis methods, applied for damage assessment of a real-world structure. The structure forms a typical sample of bridges in the Swiss Roadway Network, comprising a representative sample of a traditional concrete bridge engineering approach.

The monitoring campaign comprises two phases:

Phase I – Monitoring during Controlled Damage. In this phase, conducted in November 2019, measurements and non-destructive-evaluation techniques have been applied on the bridge, while localized damage scenarios have been artificially introduced. This report is concerned with the analysis of the continuous monitoring technologies, namely the processing of data obtained from accelerometers and strain sensors. The report on the use of Non-Destructive Evaluation (NDE) technologies, such as Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) and Ultrasound scans, is offered in the separate [report R191102](#), compiled by our partner *recontec*. The obtained results in this phase, clearly indicate the potential of continuous monitoring methods (relying on measurements of acceleration and strain) for quantifying the effect of the controllably induced artificial damages on the bridge. These artificial damages were chosen to represent structural faults of increasing intensity.

Phase II – Monitoring during Demolition. In this phase, executed in January 2020, lower cost accelerometer sensors were used to check the tracking of damage evolution during demolition.

In both phases, the derivation of clear indicators of damage, which cannot only detect but also locale damage for such typical bridge structures, demonstrates the clear value of Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) for the efficient management of ageing infrastructure, since the derived Damage Indicators be exploited to support decisions on maintenance, rehabilitation and replacement.

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I Introduction

Ponte Moesa Campagnola (PMC) was a three-span bridge crossing the river Moesa between San Vittore (GR) and Roveredo (GR), as part of the Swiss highway A13. The progressed degradation of the bridge led to its decommission and replacement with a new bypass, comprised of a 2.5 km-long tunnel and a new 106 m long bridge next to the studied structure. Prior to its planned demolition in January 2020, PMC was exposed to artificial damage scenarios and the dynamic response was recorded under ambient and forced excitation loadings. The acquired data have been used for the identification of the dynamic characteristics, as well as for the verification of damage-detection methods, featuring the potential of Structural Health Monitoring tool to support the condition assessment of ageing infrastructure, as well as to timely detect structural damage. An overview of the studied PMC bridge and the new bypass is provided in Figure 1, with representative pictures of the progressively induced damages in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Ponte Moesa Campagnola (left) and new bypass of Roveredo (right).

Figure 2: Characteristic pictures of the structural degradation of the bridge as-was, prior to the campaign: concrete spalling and exposed rusted reinforcement (a) at the support of the main girders, (b) at the top slab of the girder box, (c) at the abutments and (d) highly corroded bearings.

1.1 Bridge description

PMC was a 93.5 m long and 11.15 m wide pre-stressed concrete girder bridge. The longitudinal axis of the bridge was slightly curved, and the supports were skewed in an angle of approx. 30°. The approximate bridge orientation was East-West, pointing to Grono (GR) in the east, and to Bellinzona (TI) in the west. The bridge dimensions are summarized in Figure 3. The bridge cross-section consists of a 1.5 m high and 5.7 m wide single cell concrete box-girder with a top slab cantilevering approx. 2.75 m in both sides of the transverse direction. Detailed dimensions of the cross-section are provided in Figure 3c. The girder is prestressed longitudinally by eight VSL tendons, four in each web. The cables lay in parabolic shapes inside the webs, as shown in Figure 4a. The tendons are anchored by anchor heads, as shown in Figure 4b. According to the available documentation, each cable was prestressed up to 246.1 tons and released to 220 tons afterwards, while the nominal capacity of the anchor heads reaches 260 tons. Over the piers and the abutments massive, reinforced crossbeams transfer the vertical loads from the webs and slabs into the supports, via shear and transverse bending.

Figure 3: (a) ground plan, (b) longitudinal section and (c) cross-section of the bridge.

The bridge is supported by concrete-abutments at the riversides and concrete-piers. The abutments are partially embedded in the riverbanks, as shown in Figure 5a and b. The bridge-deck is connected to the abutments through two (probably friction) bearing, as shown in Figure 5c. The intermediate supports are concrete pillars, measuring approximately 5 m in height and width and 1.5 m in depth. An overview of the piers is provided in Figure 5d. The piers are founded on raft footings, which are embedded inside

the riverbed to prevent scouring. The bridge deck is connected to the piers through bearings that primarily offer vertical support. The bridge deck is considered to function as a continuous beam with simple supports, while the deteriorated state of the bearings could compromise their decoupling performance.

Figure 4: Drawings of prestressed tendons: (a) ground view and longitudinal section of the west half of the bridge, (b) detail showing the anchor heads at the abutment support and (c) detail showing the tendons in the cross-section of one main girder.

Figure 5: Bridge support: (a) east abutment, (b) west abutment, (c) zoom into the bearings of the west abutment and (d) view of the bridge pier in the river.

(d) view of the intermediate pier-supports.

2 Monitoring Campaign

2.1 Measurement Campaigns

As mentioned in the abstract, the studied structure was monitored in two phases.

Phase I – Monitoring during Controlled Damage

This first campaign was conducted in November 2019 and aimed at i) the derivation of robust damage indicators, based on typical continuous (also referred to as permanent) monitoring technologies, such as acceleration and strain recordings, and ii) at the parallel use of state of the art Non-Destructive Evaluation (NDE) techniques, namely Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) and Ultrasound scans, for structural assessment. This report focuses on the first part, i.e. the processing of data obtained from accelerometers and strain sensors. The report on the use of Non-Destructive Evaluation (NDE) technologies is offered in the separate report R191102, compiled by our partner *recontec*. During this phase, artificial damage scenarios were progressively introduced, to study the effect of damage on the monitored signals, which in turns allows for both detection as well localization of damage.

The following artificial damage scenarios were executed at the positions defined in Figure 6:

- Reinforcement exposure at positions I, II and III.
- Prestressed tendon exposure and cut at position II.
- Reduction of the cross-section of the main girder with boreholes at position IV.

The above-described artificial damages are demonstrated in Figure 7. The time log of the damaging activities, including the definition of the damaged states, along with the conducted ambient and forced vibration recordings, which followed its damage scenario, are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Time log for Phase I – Monitoring during Controlled Damage, listing of the Damage Scenarios

Date	Time	Damage State	Notes
26.11.2019	07:30 - 11:55		Exposure of rebars at pos. I, II
	11:55 - 13:05	1	
	13:05 - 15:55		Exposure of rebars at pos. I, II
	15:55 - 13:00 (27.11)	2	
	27.11.2019	13:00 - 17:00	Exposure of rebars at pos. I, II and III
	17:00 - 08:00 (28.11)	3	
28.11.2019	08:00 - 08:10		Reinforcement exposure and cut at pos. II, III
	08:47 - 08:57		Drilling at pos. IV
	09:40 - 10:01		
	11:10 - 11:25		
	11:53 - 12:08		
	12:08 - 13:26	4	

28.11.2019	13:26-13:46		Cutting half of one prestressed tendon (pos. II) Drilling at pos. IV
		5	Half Prestressed tendon cut (pos. II)
28.11.2019	14:13-15:22		Cutting the remaining half of the prestressed tendon (pos. II) Drilling at pos. IV
28.11.2019	15:22-08:00 (29.11)	6	Whole prestressed tendon cut (pos. II)
29.11.2019	08:00-08:56		Drilling at pos. IV
	08:56-09:33	7	

Figure 6: Position and description of progressively induced damage scenarios.

Figure 7: Phase I - Artificial damage scenarios: (a) Reinforcement exposure at pos. I, II, (b) reinforcement exposure and cut at pos. III, (c) Prestressed tendon exposure and cut at pos. II, (d) cross-section reduction via boreholes at pos. IV.

Phase II – Monitoring during Demolition

The second monitoring campaign was conducted in January 2020, during the planned demolition of the bridge. Prior to its demolition, the bridge was instrumented with triaxial accelerometers and the response was recorded during the forced vibrations generated during construction works and demolition activities. The demolition of the bridge was conducted by means of a construction-drilling machine. As demonstrated in Figure 8, the demolition started by removing the south cantilever part of the cross-section at the middle span and progressed with drilling the main girders, leading to the total separation of the bridge-deck into two independent parts.

Figure 8: Phase II – Monitoring during Demolition: (a) Removal of the south cantilever wings at the middle span, (b) Drilling the main south girder, (c) progressed destruction of the south girder, (d) total separation of the bridge at the middle span.

2.2 Sensor layout and data acquisition

Phase I – Monitoring during Controlled Damage

During Phase I, seven high-sensitivity triaxial accelerometers Syscom MR3000C were deployed (Error! Reference source not found.a). These accelerometers provide a dynamic range of 100 dB @ $\pm 4g$, measuring at a sampling rate of 200 Hz. The integrated digitizer yields 24-bit resolution while the nominal RMS noise level is lower than $10 \mu g / \sqrt{Hz}$. Despite the wireless capabilities of the sensor nodes, a cabled network was installed to guarantee synchronous data acquisition and increased quality of data, since the aim is for this case study to serve as a benchmark for the bridge monitoring community.

Figure 9: Phase I - Instrumentation: (a) high sensitivity accelerometers Syscom MR3000C, (b) Distributed fiber optic sensors, (c) portable plate vibrator

To capture a rich representation of the dynamic response of the bridge, six measurement setups were implemented by moving the portable accelerometer sensor boxes (Figure 10 a-f). In all cases, the acceleration sensors were placed on the upper side of the bridge deck, while the positions of the sensor nodes 1 to 3 were kept constant for all setups.

Figure 10: Accelerometer positions, Phase I - setups 1-6 (a-f) and Phase II - setup 1 (g)

In addition, distributed fiber optic sensors (FOS, **Error! Reference source not found.**) were placed at critical locations of the main girders, at the positions marked in Figure 11. The dynamic data acquisition was conducted by means of the LUNA ODiSI 6000 optical interrogator at a maximum sampling rate of 33.3 Hz and a minimum spatial resolution of 2.6 mm. Finally, temperature sensors were placed at various positions inside the girder box.

While the data was recorded continuously, special effort was put in order to obtain both ambient and forced vibration measurements between clearly separable damage states, per Table 1. Forced

vibrations were generated by means of a portable plate vibrator (Error! Reference source not found.c) that was placed at Positions A and B, corresponding to the middle points of the middle and the east span respectively. Additionally, roving excitation was applied next to all measuring points by moving the vibrator next to the measuring accelerometers. While the amplitude and the frequency of the applied force were not measured directly, two different amplitude levels were applied, namely lower and higher amplitude, by varying the frequency of the vibrator: by increasing the rotating frequency the centrifugal force increases, leading to higher excitation amplitude.

Figure 11: Phase I - Distributed fiber optic sensor positions.

Phase II – Monitoring during Demolition

Figure 12: Low-cost MEMS accelerometer sensors used in Phase II; custom-made by the Chair of Structural Mechanics & Monitoring at ETH Zürich.

During Phase II, low-cost customized triaxial accelerometer nodes - based on MEMS technology - were deployed. These are illustrated in Figure 11. The positions of these sensors are indicated in Figure 10g. The NI c9188 data acquisition device was used for the acquisition of the recordings. The measured response includes forced vibrations during construction activities at the vicinity of the bridge, as well as the vibrations generated during demolition activities.

3 Analysis results

3.1 Operational Modal Analysis

Initially the dynamic characteristics of the structure are identified based on *ambient* acceleration (vibration) measurements extracted at “healthy” state. The term “healthy” here refers to our baseline or, in other words, the condition of the bridge at the first instance when the monitoring system was installed. Such a baseline state is needed for serving as a reference (point 0) against which additional damage to the bridge is detected and quantified. This is a main principle of continuous monitoring: when relying on data-driven analysis and unless a prior model of the bridge is available – we may only quantify damage relative to the original state of bridge at the time when the monitoring system is deployed. However, it should be noted, that in case of existing damage, a vibration based monitoring system can detect the presence of such a damage since this typically results in loss of the symmetric modal properties of the system. Thus, damage detection can be possible even without a reference state, but when damage quantification is of interest, then it is required to refer to a baseline state. This is thus what is here deemed the “healthy” (baseline) state: the condition of the bridge at the first time of deployment of the monitoring system.

Secondly, it is important to define what the term *ambient* measurements means. In vibration-based Structural Health Monitoring (SHM), the term ambient is used to denote measurements of the bridge response under operational loads, which are characterized by a broad spectral (frequency) content, such as traffic or wind. As this bridge has been closed to traffic, we mostly here refer to measurements when no significant external forcing (e.g. via the vibrator machine) is applied on the bridge.

Ambient vibration measurements can be fed into standardized by now Operational Modal Analysis (OMA) methods, which can be accomplished via dedicated OMA software such as MACEC or ARTEMIS. We use our own MATLAB implementation of a Stochastic Subspace Identification (SSI) algorithm, to extract the modal frequencies and modal shapes of the bridge through ambient acceleration recordings. Figure 13 summarizes the identified modal characteristics up to the 7th natural vibration mode. The first characteristic mode consists mainly of horizontal components and can be attributed to the curvature of the bridge in longitudinal direction. The remaining identified modes can be characterized as primarily vertical modes, combining bending and rotational displacement patterns.

Figure 13: Operational modal analysis, identified modes.

3.2 Vibration-based Damage detection & Localization via Accelerometer Sensors

For the purposes of damage detection, a damage index (DI) based on variations of the first spatial derivative of the modal shapes has been implemented, defined as follows:

$$DI_{kij}^{DS} = \frac{|(\varphi_{k,j}^{DS} - \varphi_{i,j}^{DS})| - |(\varphi_{k,j}^{ref} - \varphi_{i,j}^{ref})|}{|(\varphi_{k,j}^{ref} - \varphi_{i,j}^{ref})|}$$

where:

- DI_{kij}^{DS} : mode j , damage index evaluation between node i and k idamaged state DS
- $\varphi_{i,j}^{DS}$: for mode j , modal displacement at node i in damaged state DS
- $\varphi_{i,j}^{ref}$: for mode j , modal displacement at node i in reference state ref

Figure 14: Phase I – Monitoring during controlled damage, Ambient loading; damage detection and localization: (a) studied modes, (b) Damage index estimations for mode F_2 , (c) Damage index estimations for mode F_5 and (d)

corresponding sensor positions.

In Phase I, by considering the healthy state as reference, the DI yields the residuals for all sensor combinations for each mode. For the case of ambient recordings (Figure 14), the DI indicates changes between nodes #4, #1 and #6 for the modes F_2 and F_5 respectively. For both modes, the DI increases almost monotonically with accumulating damage. Node #4 is placed near the bridge support where damage scenarios I and II take place, while nodes #1 and #6 are placed on the west span, where the damage scenario IV develops (Figure 7).

In Phase II, which pertains to monitoring of the bridge during demolition, the identified DI amplitude (Figure 15Figure 8) follows the progressive degradation of the bridge, as the demolition procedure evolves. Significant differences in terms of residuals are detected between sensors #4 and #1. The former is placed in vicinity of the damage (Figure 8a), while the latter is placed on the east span of the main girder.

Figure 15: Phase II - Monitoring during demolition; damage detection and localization: (a) studied mode, (b) Damage index estimations for mode F_3 and (c) corresponding sensor positions. It is mentioned that the node numbers in (b) do not coincide with the sensor labels in (a) and (c).

During Phase I, in addition to the ambient vibrations, stronger vibrations have been introduced with a vibrating device (see Fig. 9c). With these stronger excitations, the frequency response function (FRF)

between pairs of sensors can be evaluated:

$$FRF_{ij} = \frac{P_{ii}}{P_{jj}}$$

where FRF_{ij} designates the frequency response function between sensing nodes i , and j and P_{ii} is the power spectral density of the signal measured at node i , evaluated using Welch's method.

Changes in the FRF may, among other spurious reasons for changes in dynamic behavior that include temperature, amplitude, and nature of loading, indicate the onset of damage. An example of changes in the FRF due to damage is shown in Figure 16 for measurement setup 5 (see Figure 10e). In order to reduce the influence of temperature, only measurements from the early mornings of November 28 (DS3) and November 29 (DS6) are presented. A reduction in the frequency values that correspond to the peak values in the FRF may indicate a loss of stiffness that is typically associated with damage.

Figure 16: Phase I – Monitoring during controlled damage, loading via a Vibrating Device; Changes in the FRFs between nodes (a) 3 and 54 in transversal direction, (b) 3 and 55 in transversal direction, and (c) 3 and 55 in vertical direction. All sensor locations refer to the measurement setup 5 for measurements taken in the early the morning.

Changes in the FRF may be evaluated in a more systematic manner using a collinearity metric called frequency response assurance criterion (FRAC):

$$FRAC_{ij} = \frac{\left| FRF_{ij}^{refT} FRF_{ij}^{dam} \right|^2}{\left| FRF_{ij}^{refT} FRF_{ij}^{ref} \right| \left| FRF_{ij}^{damT} FRF_{ij}^{dam} \right|}$$

where *ref* stands for a reference state and *dam* stands for damaged state. The FRAC is typically evaluated within a limited range of frequency values. An example of changes in the FRAC, which can be considered a damage-sensitive feature (DSF), is shown in Fig. 16 for the FRF between nodes 57 and 1, in the frequency range between 43 and 46 Hz. The introduced damage translates to a clear change in the FRF that leads to an increase in the FRAC.

Figure 17 Changes in the vertical FRF between nodes 7 and 1 (a) and the corresponding evaluation of the FRAC metric (b).

Sensor nodes 1 to 3 measured continuously at fixed positions throughout the measurement. Thus, the changes in FRF between sensors 2 and 3 are evaluated for 30-second windows of the signal over the duration of the entire day. The evolution of $FRAC_{23}$ for the signals recorded in all three directions on is shown in Fig. 17, for the frequency range from 5 to 45Hz. As can be seen, the amplitude of the loading results in significant changes in the FRAC, while the values during the night are more stable. As a result, any structural-health monitoring application should account for the amplitude of loading.

Figure 18: Changes in the FRF evaluated using the FRAC on November 28th. It can be observed that increased loading amplitudes generally translate to changes in the FRF for all three directions: vertical (V), transversal (T), and normal (N).

Considering the small variabilities in the FRAC, values that are observed even during the night, where loading and temperature conditions can be considered stable, the distribution of FRAC values are derived for 2-hour windows. The resulting distributions are shown in Fig.18a for the longitudinal direction and show a clear change after the damage introduced on November 28. By using a

probabilistic way to compare the distributions (in this case the Kullback-Leibler divergence), changes with respect to the reference period (November 28, 00:00-02:00) can be evaluated in a robust manner and show promising potential (see Fig. 18b).

Figure 19 Changes in the probability density function (PDF) of two-hour windows of the FRF23 in the longitudinal direction (a) and assessment of the Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence with the reference time window (28-Nov 00:00-02:00) as a quantitative indicator of changes in the FRF (b). After the introduction of damage on November 28, a change in the distribution of the FRF can be observed.

3.3 Damage detection & Localization via Distributed Strain Sensing (FOS)

During Phase I, additionally to the deployed accelerometer sensors, Fiber optic sensors (FOS) were placed at the positions marked in Figure 11 in order to evaluate their sensitivity to the artificially induced damage scenarios. As shown in Figure 20a, the FOS at all three positions detected the structural degradation that resulted from cutting the half of one prestressed tendon at position II (Figure 6).

The FOS measuring shear strains at position III appears to be the most sensitive to the cross-sectional reduction of the prestressed tendon, despite being the most remotely placed sensor from the damaged position II. This can be attributed to potential redistribution of shear forces. Figure 20b illustrates the dynamic response of the FOS placed at position II during forced vibration of the bridge. Although the sampling rate (33.3 Hz) allows the detection of the fundamental mode (see Figure 19c), the low signal to noise ratio does not allow for further exploitation of distributed FOS system for the dynamic analysis and identification of the bridge.

Figure 20: Phase I - Fiber optic sensors: (a) static measurements at different damage states, (b) dynamic measurement at position 2 (forced vibration), and (c) frequency-domain analysis of the dynamic measurement at position 2.

4 Discussion & Conclusions

4.1 Main Findings

The testing and data-driven assessment of Ponte Moesa Campagnola has offered a unique opportunity to establish an SHM benchmark via monitoring of the structural response of a real highway bridge at controllably induced damage states of increasing severity. In Phase I of the monitoring campaign, the bridge was permanently monitored during a period of four days, during which various artificial damage scenarios were introduced, while in Phase II, a lower-cost monitoring system was deployed to monitor the bridge during its planned demolition.

Different sensor technologies, excitation sources, and damage sensitive metrics have been implemented. The main findings of this campaign are summarized in the following bullets:

- It was shown that modal properties can be used to construct indicators that allow damage detection and localization. For the identification of the modal (dynamic) characteristics of the bridge during Phase I, two different input excitations have been considered, namely ambient excitation, which comprises unknown vibration sources from the surrounding environment (wind, traffic etc.), and forced excitation, generated through a portable plate vibrator. Operational modal analysis enabled the identification up to ten characteristic modes of vibration, based on ambient recordings. This demonstrates the powerful potential of such techniques, when adopted in the context of permanent monitoring installations, since they are freed from the requirement to control or measure the input excitation (loads).
- The characteristic frequencies of the vibrational response have been identified and they lie in the range between 4 and 20 Hz, which is typical for massive concrete bridges. Despite the apparent simple geometry of the bridge, its modal shapes demonstrate significant complexity even in the low frequency range. Horizontal and torsional components govern the response, exposing the significant effect of the mild curvature along the longitudinal axis to the measured dynamic response. In terms of structural assessment, ignoring the three dimensional effects in that case would lead to erroneous results.
- Introducing artificial damage scenarios allowed us to study the performance of various damage detection indicators. Evaluating the differences in the identified modal characteristics at different damage states can only be useful in detecting the existence of permanent damage that affects the global dynamic behavior of the structure. Assuming a sufficiently dense grid of sensors, the evaluation of the spatial derivatives of the identified modal shapes showed promising results in localizing damage between sensor-pairs, as well as in detecting the damage accumulation. One step further, criteria that are based on variations in the frequency response function have been implemented in combination with a probabilistic distance metric (KL-divergence), providing robust indicators of damage, as well as promising results in terms of damage localization. The inclusion of a probabilistic perspective is important for this type of analyses, where uncertainty and variability is naturally expected due to the uncertainty in the measurements (noise, environmental effects).
 - The use of distributed fiber optic sensors (based on the LUNA technology that is

based on the Rayleigh backscatter phenomenon) demonstrates sufficient sensitivity in sensing structural damage. The sensors placed at the vicinity of the eastern abutment, oriented accordingly in order to capture changes in shear strains, yielded the maximum sensitivity to damage introduced in the intermediate supports. Measuring the dynamic response through distributed fiber optic sensors did not provide satisfactory results due to relatively low sampling rate and insufficient signal to noise ratio.

In conclusion, this study has enabled the evaluation of sensor technologies and suited data-analysis tools for damage assessment on a real-world structure. The results demonstrate the promising potential and the additional value that permanent monitoring could add to ageing infrastructure. Although assessing the structural health based on sensor data consists nowadays a mature research domain, permanent monitoring has yet to be established in engineering practice. Structural Health Monitoring can act as a supplement to the practice of scheduled inspection, supporting the timely, accurate and automated detection of damage. This in turn enables the support of decisions on optimal maintenance planning and ultimately the extension of the life span of existing infrastructure facilities. The exploitation of such data-driven condition assessment methods and their incorporation into maintenance planning is deemed as an eminent requirement towards materializing a sustainable and more resilient infrastructure footprint.

4.2 Challenges

Given the restricted timeline and the limited resources, certain aspects that are relevant to permanent monitoring installations have been neglected during this experimental campaign. Permanent monitoring installations and future experiments should take into account the following points:

- Environmental conditions and vibration amplitude influence the identified dynamic characteristics and consequently the performance in terms of damage prediction. In order to prevent false positives in real and permanent applications of in-service structures, a training phase with varying levels of excitation and environmental conditions would be suggested.
- Sensors and data acquisition components have shorter life spans, compared to the monitored structure. In view of permanent installations, sensor diagnostic routines should be integrated into the analysis, while regular maintenance / replacement of hardware components should be planned, in order to eliminate false alarms and monitoring downtimes.
- In the present case study, the evaluated damage scenarios relate to relatively advanced state of structural degradation. Future work should resolve around the questions: what is the minimum damage level that a monitoring system should be able to detect and what would be the necessary instrumentation to achieve this performance level? This will facilitate the cost-benefit analysis for permanent monitoring installations that are able to support decisions for efficient retrofit interventions.